

SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION ON THE BASIS OF KRASHEN'S THEORY AFTER PUBERTY (I+1)

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Annotation: *This paper explores second language acquisition (SLA) after puberty through the lens of Stephen Krashen's Input Hypothesis, particularly the concept of $i+1$. It discusses how language learners beyond the critical period face cognitive, affective, and environmental challenges, yet can still achieve high proficiency with comprehensible input slightly above their current level. The article reviews the Critical Period Hypothesis, empirical research on post-puberty learners, and pedagogical implications of applying $i+1$ in teaching. The study concludes that while naturalistic acquisition may be limited, structured exposure to meaningful input can foster continuous progress and communicative competence.*

Key words: *Second language acquisition, Krashen, $i+1$, puberty, critical period, input hypothesis, communicative competence*

ОСВОЕНИЕ ВТОРОГО ЯЗЫКА НА ОСНОВЕ ТЕОРИИ КРАШЕНА ПОСЛЕ ПОЛОВОГО СОЗРЕВАНИЯ (I+1)

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Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматривается процесс усвоения второго языка после периода полового созревания на основе гипотезы ввода Стивена Крашена, в частности концепции $i+1$. Анализируются когнитивные, аффективные и социальные трудности, с которыми сталкиваются учащиеся, а также возможности достижения высокого уровня владения языком при использовании понятного ввода, немного превышающего их текущие знания. Рассматриваются гипотеза критического периода, эмпирические исследования и педагогические выводы применения $i+1$. Заключается, что, несмотря на ограничения естественного усвоения, целенаправленное обучение с*

использованием значимого ввода способствует прогрессу и развитию коммуникативной компетенции.

Ключевые слова: Освоение второго языка, Крашен, $i+1$, половое созревание, критический период, гипотеза ввода, коммуникативная компетентность

BALOG'AT YOSHIDAN KEYIN KRASHEN NAZARIYASI ASOSIDA IKKINCHI TILNI EGALLASH ($i+1$)

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola pubertat davridan keyingi ikkinchi tilni o'zlashtirish jarayonini Stiven Krashening Input gipotezasi, xususan $i+1$ tamoyili asosida tahlil qiladi. Til o'rganuvchilarning ushbu davrdan keyin uchraydigan kognitiv, affektiv va ijtimoiy muammolari hamda tushunarli va biroz yuqori darajadagi kirish ma'lumotlari orqali yuqori natijalarga erishish imkoniyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqolada kritik davr gipotezasi, empirik tadqiqotlar hamda o'qitishda $i+1$ ni qo'llashning pedagogik ahamiyati yoritilgan. Xulosa o'rnida, tabiiy o'zlashtirish cheklangan bo'lsa-da, maqsadli va mazmunli material asosida o'qitish doimiy rivojlanish va kommunikativ kompetensiyaga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ikkinchi tilni o'zlashtirish, Krashen, $i+1$, balog'at yoshi, tanqidiy davr, kirish gipotezasi, kommunikativ kompetensiya

Introduction

Language learning is central to personal development and national progress. In Uzbekistan, significant attention has been paid to strengthening foreign language education, particularly English, as a means of integration into the global academic and economic space. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev (2019, 2020) has repeatedly emphasized that mastering foreign languages is one of the key competencies of the modern generation, and reforms in the education sector aim to ensure competitive specialists for the future.

Second language acquisition (SLA) after puberty presents unique challenges due to neurological, cognitive, and affective factors. Unlike children, adolescents and adults require more structured input and conscious learning strategies to acquire the

language in a proper level. The purpose of this study is to analyze SLA after puberty through Krashen's Input Hypothesis, focusing on the $i+1$ principle, and to provide recommendations for optimizing language learning environments in line with Uzbekistan's educational reforms.

Literature Review

The study of SLA has developed into a rich interdisciplinary field. Stephen Krashen's theory (Krashen, 1982, 1985) remains one of the most influential frameworks, particularly his Input Hypothesis, which states that learners acquire language when exposed to comprehensible input slightly above their current level ($i+1$). This framework explores how gradual process with the highlight of a mere higher level can guarantee to learn the language properly. After puberty, the critical period hypothesis suggests a decline in natural acquisition ability (Lenneberg, 1967; Singleton & Ryan, 2004). The explanation for that is the plasticity of the brain decrease and it affects language learning process. However, researchers argue that adults compensate through cognitive strategies, motivation, and explicit learning (Birdsong, 2014). Although there are physical and mental difficulties in learning and acquiring the language in adulthood, such as family and work matters; and overthinking procrastination, with the aid of other factors such as motivation and suitable language learning instruction with proper method may actually help the learners to speak this language with native-like level.

Recent studies highlight the importance of affective factors in post-puberty SLA. Anxiety, motivation, and self-confidence play a vital role in determining outcomes (Horwitz, 2017). Moreover, the integration of technology and task-based learning environments offers opportunities for providing authentic $i+1$ input (Lightbown & Spada, 2013).

In the Uzbek context, scholars (Abdukarimov, 2021; Karimova, 2022) emphasize that creating supportive environments and modernizing curricula are essential to improving outcomes for high school and university learners. Thus, the literature demonstrates that SLA after puberty requires an adapted pedagogical framework that balances input, practice, and emotional support.

Research Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative-descriptive approach, supported by document analysis and secondary data from recent research articles. The research philosophy aligns with an interpretivist perspective, emphasizing understanding over measurement.

- Research Design: Descriptive review of Krashen's theory applied to post-puberty learners.
- Sampling: Target group – adolescents (14–18 years) and adults in Uzbekistan's high schools and universities.
- Data Sources: Academic articles, policy documents, and presidential speeches related to language education.
- Research Strategy: Literature-based analysis supported by thematic categorization (input, affective factors, educational reforms). The students are provided with all the required materials and the teacher acts like an instructor to direct the learners to fulfill the tasks.
- Ethics: All sources properly cited in APA format; no personal data collected.

This methodology ensures reliability through cross-referencing multiple sources and validity by grounding findings in both theory and educational policy.

Analysis and Results

Analysis of the reviewed literature and policy documents shows that:

1. Post-puberty learners face more difficulties in natural acquisition compared to children, supporting the critical period hypothesis.
2. Krashen's $i+1$ principle remains effective when applied with structured teaching methods, especially task-based learning, reading programs, and technology-mediated input.
3. Motivation and affective support are decisive factors for adolescents and adults. Programs that integrate confidence-building and low-anxiety environments show improved outcomes (Horwitz, 2017).
4. Uzbekistan's reforms in language policy (Mirziyoyev, 2020) create institutional support for SLA, but implementation challenges persist in rural areas where resources are limited.
5. Practical implication: Teachers must design activities that provide comprehensible input slightly beyond learners' current abilities while ensuring scaffolding and continuous exposure.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The research demonstrates that while puberty introduces challenges in SLA, effective application of Krashen's $i+1$ principle allows adolescents and adults to

achieve high levels of proficiency. The key lies in providing structured, meaningful input in low-anxiety environments, coupled with motivational strategies.

Recommendations:

- Develop teacher training focused on applying Krashen's principles in Uzbek classrooms.
- Increase integration of technology to provide authentic i+1 input.
- Expand reforms to ensure equal access to resources in urban and rural schools.
- Encourage further research into the role of affective factors and cross-cultural differences in SLA after puberty.

In line with the President's vision, strengthening SLA for youth will not only improve individual opportunities but also contribute to Uzbekistan's broader goal of building a competitive, multilingual society.

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